

The Ethical Motivation of Memory Work

Abstract

In his Zürich Lectures from 1997 W.G. Sebald argued that there is a lacuna in German literature concerning the Allies' firebombing of German civilians and German cities during WW2. According to Sebald, the German writers did not write about what they had been witnessing and thereby they failed to convey the traumatizing events into the memories of a whole generation. In cases where a group has experienced and participated in traumatizing events, the memory of these events might be distorted, misrepresented or not represented at all in the collective memory. I want to consider whether in such cases we can talk of collective amnesia, as it allows me to focus on some of the mechanisms at stake in collective memory. Further, I will argue that what I call "memory work" involves an active commitment to self-understanding also at a collective level. Once we understand better the notion of memory work, we can understand why and how it is ethically motivated. The notion of memory work will prove to be relevant beyond the study of collective memory itself; I will argue that to memory work is a necessary condition for making a sincere and genuine public apology and thereby to propose a reconfiguration of the landscape of collective memory.

Keywords: Collective memory, hermeneutic experience, self-understanding, trauma, tradition, reflection, affectivity.

1. Introduction: Is collective amnesia possible?

In his Zürich Lectures from 1997 the German author W.G. Sebald¹ argued that there is a lacuna in German literature concerning the Allies' firebombing of German cities during WW2. As a result of this lacuna, Sebald claims, German collective memory has been blocked in such a way that what is recalled from the firebombing is either reduced to clichés about everyday life during the war or it is transformed into collective fantasies about how quickly and promising German cities arose from the ruins and are turned into vibrant futuristic cities full of promise. According to Sebald, the German writers did not write about the horrors they had been witnessing but instead they were busy trying to improve their own public image after the war. For that reason, a whole generation did not have any shared, collective memory of these events. To put it differently, the traumatic memories had not been *inscribed into language*, to use a very helpful phrase from Dorothée Legrand² (2024, forthcoming).

¹ Winfried Georg Sebald: *Luftkrieg und Literatur*. München 1999

² Dorothée Legrand: "Does language put the world at the limit of phenomenology – or how does one survive?" in Stefano Michali and Valeria Bizzari (Eds.) *The New Yearbook for Phenomenology*, Vol. XXII: Liminal Phenomena: A Phenomenological Investigation. (Forthcoming)

According to Sebald, the eagerness to rebuild Germany made the total destruction look as a successful beginning: “Nicht als das Grauensvolle Ende einer kollektiven Aberration erscheint also diese totale Zerstörung, sondern, sozusagen, als die erste Stufe des erfolgreichen Wiederaufbaus.“³:

Der inzwischen bereits legendäre und, in einer Hinsicht, tatsächlich bewundernswerte deutsche Wiederaufbau, der, nach den von den Kriegsgegnern⁴ angerichteten Verwüstungen, einer in sukzessiven Phasen sich vollziehenden zweiten Liquidierung der eigenen Vorgeschichte gleichkam, unterband durch die geforderte Arbeitsleistung sowohl als durch die Schaffung einer neuen, gesichtslosen Wirklichkeit von vornherein jegliche Rückerinnerung, richtete die Bevölkerung ausnahmslos auf die Zukunft aus und verpflichtete sie zum Schweigen über das, was ihr widerfahren war.⁵

Selbst die vielberufene, programmatisch einen unbestechlichen Wirklichkeitssinn sich vorsetzende Trümmerliteratur, in der es nach Heinrich Bölls Bekenntnis hauptsächlich um das ging, “was wir ... bei der Heimkehr vorfanden”, erweist sich bei näherer Betrachtung als sein auf die individuelle und kollektive Amnesie bereits eingestimmtes, wahrscheinlich von vorbewussten Prozessen der Selbstzensur gesteuertes Instrument zur Verschleierung einer auf keinen Begriff mehr zu bringenden Welt.⁶

As a result of the collective amnesia and collective censorship: “Die finstersten Aspekte des von der weitaus überwiegenden Mehrheit der deutschen Bevölkerung miterlebten Schlußakts der Zerstörung blieben so ein schandbares, mit einer Art Tabu behaftetes Familiengeheimnis, das man vielleicht nicht einmal sich selber eingestehen konnte“ (ibid.). To sum up, Sebald writes: „in solcher Präokkupation mit der Nachbesserung des Bildes, das man von sich überliefern wollte, lag, meines Erachtens, einer der wichtigsten Gründe für die Unfähigkeit

Dorothee Legrand: “It goes with(out) saying: The disruptive habit of speaking” in Line Ryberg Ingerslev and Karl Mertens (Eds.) *Phenomenology of Broken Habits: Philosophical and Psychological Perspectives on Habitual Action* in (eds.) London 2024.

³ Sebald: *Luftkrieg und Literatur*, 14.

⁴ The English translation specifies that “Kriegsgegner” in this context means “Germany’s wartime enemies” (Winfried Georg Sebald: *On the Natural History of Destruction*, London 2004, 7). It should therefore in this context be mentioned that what was new in Sebald’s lectures was how they took up what was hitherto considered a taboo; the suffering of German civilians were described in a non-revisionistic context: “Der Erinnerung, der sie zu ihrem Recht verhelfen, ist kein revisionistisches Argument eingeschrieben. Sie haben keine politische, sondern eine literarische und therapeutische Agenda, die darin besteht, traumatischen Geschichtserfahrungen nach einer gewissen Latenzzeit die Chance einer bewussten Wiederaufnahme und Aufarbeitung zu geben.“ (Aleida Assmann: *Der lange Schatten der Vergangenheit. Erinnerungskultur und Geschichtspolitik*. München 2021, 186, see also Roland Breuer: “‘Heimkehr’ Description de l’aberration d’une espèce“ in *Cahiers d’Etudes Germanique*, vol. 69, 2015, 175-188.

⁵ Ibid., 15.

⁶ Ibid., 18.

einer ganzen Generation deutscher Autoren, das, was sie gesehen hatten, aufzuzeichnen und einzubringen in unser Gedächtnis⁷“. It is this latter aspect that is of interest to me.

In what follows, I will consider the ethical implications of Sebald’s thesis of collective amnesia. *What does it mean for a group to remember and what happens when memory work is not carried out?* By contrast, therefore, to describing the possible mechanisms involved in collective forgetting⁸, I will argue that as a collective, we remember what has happened by thanks to the process described by Dorothee Legrand as a way of *inscribing* certain events *into language*⁹. In the context of collective memory, it can be argued that to inscribe something into language is to convey certain happenings and events into the minds of a generation and thereby to make the events available for future generations such that they can be remembered onwards. We can think of the act of inscription as involving an underlying idea that *Saying* itself and *Writing* itself, as argued by Emmanuel Levinas¹⁰, is different from and by far surpasses what is said or written; the *Saying* and, in the context of collective memory, the *Writing* itself so one might support Sebald’s thesis, would have inscribed the traumatic experiences into language and thereby into the collective memory – such that future generations can be addressed by these writings. It will be the main idea in this paper to show how inscribing what has happened into language contains an *ethical address*; and when we respond to the past by responding to happenings in the past, it is a response that goes beyond a mere obligation to reproduce past memories in order to preserve the past; rather, the response consists in a commitment to (the continuation of) *plural self-reflection* – and quite concretely it carries within it a transgenerational commitment.

⁷ Ibid., 8

⁸ See Marc Augé: *Oblivion*. Translated by Marjolin de Jager. London 2004; Daniel Gyollai: “Collaborative Inhibition: A Phenomenological Perspective” in *Psychological and Phenomenological Research*, 2024, Online first: 1-19; and Aleida Assmann: *Formen des Vergessens*, Göttingen 2020.

⁹ Dorothee Legrand: “It goes with(out) saying: The disruptive habit of speaking” in Line Ryberg Ingerslev and Karl Mertens (Eds.) *Phenomenology of Broken Habits: Philosophical and Psychological Perspectives on Habitual Action* in (eds.) London 2024.

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¹⁰ Emmanuel Levinas *Otherwise than Being or Beyond Essence*. Translated by A. Lingis. Pittsburg 2006.

2. Memory work

Let's assume that groups can remember. In order to assume this, several disclaimers must be made. Group memory should *not* be understood by analogy to individual memory¹¹; a group does not forget its keys, or remembers how something felt yesterday. In assuming that a group has memory, I will not be questioning or investigating the ontological requirements for a group to be minded or for group members to have we-experiences¹² in order for the same group to be able to have shared memories. By collective memory, I also do not have in mind the sum of individual memories of the same event (like flash-bulb-memory of significant events, say 9/11, see Margalit¹³). Neither do I think of historical knowledge of lines of kings and queens, wars or inventions; nor of educational implicit or explicit narratives such as those of local or national heroism. Further, I do not think of the capacity to empathize with members of certain groups in the past. So, what *do* I mean? Whereas individual and collective memory are typically studied by different methods and different disciplines, I will approach the assumption that groups can remember to entail the following idea: for a group to be able to remember, the group members must be able to actively engage in *memory work* with regards to the past of that group. This means that I take memory work to be the activity of reflecting upon implicit collective memory schemas¹⁴ with the purpose of making them explicit for group reflection. That is, I define memory work as the act of self-reflection done by groups members concerning their diachronic group self-understanding. Memory work reflects on *implicit forms* of “collective memory”¹⁵ and whereas implicit “collective memory” is more static than the processual and

¹¹ James V. Wertsch „Collective Memory” in *Memory in Mind and Culture*. (Eds) Boyer, P. & J.V. Wertsch, Cambridge, 2009, 121-4.

¹² Hans Bernard Schmidt *We, Together: The Social ontology of Us*. Oxford: 2023; Deborah Tollefsen *Groups as Agents*, Cambridge 2015; Dan Zahavi *Being We: Phenomenological Contributions to Social Ontology*, Oxford 2025.

¹³ Avishai Margalit *The Ethics of Memory*, Harvard 2002.

¹⁴ James V. Wertsch *The Voices of Collective Remembering*, New York 2002; Astrid Erll “The hidden Power of Implicit Collective Memory” in *Memory, Mind, and Media*, 1:e14, 1-17; Frederic Bartlett *Remembering: A study in experimental and social psychology*, Cambridge 1995.

¹⁵ Maurice Halbwachs *On Collective Memory*, Chicago 1992; Hans-Georg Gadamer *Wahrheit und Methode*, Tübingen 1960; Paul Ricœur *Gedächtnis, Geschichte, Vergessen*, translated by H-D Godenkt, H.Jatho and M. Sedlaczek, München 2000; Minna-Kerttu “Collective Memory as Sedimentations of Collective Experience: Phenomenological Analysis of Post-Soviet Europe” in *Journal of the British Society for Phenomenology*, 55(4): 289-307; Astrid Erll “The Hidden Power of Implicit Collective Memory”; Thomas Fuchs “the Phenomenology of Body Memory” in *Body, memory, Metaphor; and Movement* (eds.) S. Koch, T. Fuchs, M. Summa and C. Müller, Amsterdam 2012; Thomas Fuchs „Collective Body Memory” in *Embodiment, Enactment and Culture, Investigating the Constitution of the Shared World* (eds.) C. Durt, t. Fuchs, and C. Tewes, Cambridge 2018; Edward S. Casey *Remembering* Bloomington 2000.

more *explicit* “collective remembering¹⁶”, we might say that *memory work* is characterized by the reflection done in collective remembering on the elements of collective memory. That is to say, for group members to engage in an act of reflective, diachronic group self-understanding, the group members will relate both implicit and explicit forms of cultural and historical memory with regards to the present self-understanding of the group in question. Another way to put the same point is that group members will make explicit what has hitherto taken for granted, implicitly acted out or silently kept as an unreflected part of one’s grounds for acting. Both the implicit, passive elements of affectivity and historicity that characterize the way we remember in a collective are needed just as much as the reflective work that ideally will lead us to see ourselves as members of this or that group in a new light¹⁷. The goal, we might say, of memory work is to understand better who we have become as members of this group and how we have come to see ourselves in this or that way – these would be the relevant questions pertaining to memory work.

The central set of questions in Sebald’s Zürich Lectures can thus be seen as an example of active memory work as he reflects on the lacuna in German literature concerning the Allies’ firebombing of German civilians. When defining memory work in this way, the question might lurk; why then speak of memory at all, if what is meant is rather an act of reflection? In collective memory, the passive elements of affectivity and tradition play an important role as to how we remember collectively. By affective elements I have in mind elements of culturally embodied practices such as ways of greeting, singing, moving, and traditional and ritualized ways of behaving that might be at one’s backbones, embedded in one’s ways of doing things with others. When we engage in memory work, the idea is that we try to catch some of these implicit elements of cultural belonging that we are unreflectively acting out with the aim of coming to understand them better. When Sebald asks, why didn’t anyone write about the firebombing, he poses a question for memory work; how do we understand ourselves as members of this group *without* inscribing these events into our collective mind?

Rather than insisting too strongly on the separation of individual and collective memory, I will assume that collective memory work involves individual memory work and vice versa: The

¹⁶ James V. Wertsch *The Voices of collective Remembering*, New York 2002, Jeffrey K. Olick *The Politics of Regret: On Collective Memory and Historical Responsibility*, London 2007; Sue Campbell *Relational Remembering: Rethinking the Wars of Memory*, London 2003; Sue Campbell “Our Faithfulness to the Past: Reconstructing Memory Value” in *Philosophical Psychology*, 19 (3): 361-380; Aleida Assman *Das neue Unbehagen an die Erinnerungskultur: Eine Intervention*. München 2020.

¹⁷ Line Ryberg Ingerslev „Responding to the Past: Affectivity and Reflection in Collective Remembering” (under review)

question of collective self-understanding will involve that we as individuals see ourselves as temporally and affectively belonging to a generation, a tradition, a community, or a group that we to a certain extent identify with. *Memory work* can be done by a collective in order to acquire and revise what we might think of as a diachronic collective self-understanding. By memory work, I thereby mean a reflection on past events that, to a certain extent, is *ethically motivated*. It is the ethical motivation and what might prevent or block it that is my concern in what follows.

At this point, it will be helpful to recall how Gadamer reflects on the productive role of time and the temporal distance involved in hermeneutic experiencing. We find that the temporal distance involved in memory work has a similar productive aspect to it. The temporal distance at stake in hermeneutic experience - as well as in memory work, so I will argue, - cannot be abolished or sublated without the ones co-remembering or co-experiencing the past falling into an unproductive and false understanding of the past guided by prejudice and not of prejudice that are made productive for hermeneutic understanding¹⁸. According to Gadamer, the temporal distance must be *foregrounded* in the attempt of understanding the past¹⁹. To foreground the temporal distance in the case of memory work would mean that when we engage in remembering past events and in commemoration of past events we might not have participated in ourselves, we should *not* try to reproduce the past by recalling it independently of the time passed. A productive understanding of past events or past texts is never mere reproduction or pure repetition of the past²⁰, rather it is constituted by a polarity or a tension between the implicit belonging to the past and an explicit questioning of how that belonging is even possible²¹:

So erfüllt sich der Sinn der Zugehörigkeit, d.h. das Moment der Tradition im historisch-hermeneutischen Verhalten, durch die Gemeinsamkeit grundlegender und tragender Vorurteile. Die Hermeneutik muss davon ausgehen, dass wer verstehen will, mit der Sache, die mit der Überlieferung zur Sprache kommt, verbunden ist und an die Tradition Anschluss hat oder Anschluss gewinnt, aus der die Überlieferung spricht. Auf der anderen Seite weiß das hermeneutische Bewusstsein, dass es mit dieser Sache nicht in der Weise einer fraglos selbstverständlichen Einigkeit verbunden sein kann, wie es für das ungebrochene Fortleben einer Tradition gilt. Es besteht wirklich eine Polarität von Vertrautheit und Fremdheit, auf die sich die Aufgabe der Hermeneutik gründet.²²

¹⁸ Hans-Georg Gadamer *Wahrheit und Methode*, Tübingen 1960, 296-300.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, 301.

²⁰ *Ibid.*, 301.

²¹ *Ibid.*, 300.

²² *Ibid.*, 300.

According to Gadamer, to belong to a tradition and to listen to what is being delivered over to us as members of that tradition contains a polarity that grounds the task for any hermeneutics; listening and belonging to a tradition will require a certain familiarity with what is delivered over and at the same time due to the temporal distance there will be an alterity inherent to the way we can listen and belong to that very tradition. The polarity in question is fundamental to the hermeneutical task of understanding. This is another way of saying that what is delivered over to us as tradition is at the same time experienced hermeneutically and productively in its *Wirkungsgeschichte*²³. The alienation from one's belonging to a tradition is part of what makes understanding the past a productive event²⁴.

Now, Gadamer further argues that the hermeneutic experience has to do with what is being delivered over by a tradition, and he compares the voice of the tradition being delivered over to the *voice of a 'you', (ein Du)*. When we receive what is being delivered over from the past, we listen to what is being said, like when we listen to a person. In three steps, Gadamer shows how only when we listen openly and let the past speak for itself without us wanting to master it, do we hermeneutically experience what is being delivered over to us. Importantly, to listen to what is being delivered over to us is at the same time an event in language:

Die hermeneutische Erfahrung hat es mit der *Überlieferung* zu tun. Sie ist es, die zur Erfahrung kommen soll. Überlieferung ist aber nicht einfach ein Geschehen, das man durch Erfahrung erkennt und beherrschen lernt, sondern sie ist *Sprache*, d.h. sie spricht von sich aus so wie ein Du.²⁵

We can approach or attempt to understand what is being delivered over to us in three different ways, Gadamer continues. We can look at what is being delivered over to us from history with a naïve belief that we can methodologically ignore our own historicity and set aside the temporal distance²⁶; or we can attempt to dialectically master other versions of the past with the aim of full reflection²⁷. Finally, we can attempt to foreground the productivity of historicity itself for our understanding of what is being delivered over. When the temporal distance is foregrounded, it results in a *hermeneutical openness towards the past* which itself, we might say, is ethically motivated. Just as openness is required for there to be true bonds between humans²⁸, because we acknowledge the voice of the other as a voice that speaks in me and

²³ Ibid., 305-7.

²⁴ Ibid., 307-12.

²⁵ Ibid., 363-4.

²⁶ Ibid., 364.

²⁷ Ibid., 365.

²⁸ Ibid., 367.

also against me, by analogy the past speaks as a Thou to us and in us in a way that is sometimes foreign to us and lead us to discover ourselves and the past anew:

Diese Erkenntnis und Anerkennung nun ist es, die eine dritte, die höchste Weise hermeneutischer Erfahrung ausmacht: die Offenheit für die Überlieferung, die *das wirkungsgeschichtliche Bewusstsein* besitzt. Auch sie hat eine echte Entsprechung zu der Erfahrung des Du. Im mitmenschlichen Verhalten kommt es darauf an, wie wir sahen, das Du als Du wirklich zu erfahren, d.h. seinen Anspruch nicht zu überhören und sich etwas von ihm sagen zu lassen. Dazu gehört Offenheit. Aber diese Offenheit ist am Ende nicht nur für den einen da, von dem man sich etwas sagen lassen will. Vielmehr, wer sich überhaupt etwas sagen lässt, ist auf eine grundsätzliche Weise offen. Ohne eine solche Offenheit füreinander gibt es keine echte menschliche Bindung. Zueinandergehören heißt immer zugleich Auf-einander-hören-können. Wenn zwei einander verstehen, so heißt das ja nicht, dass einer den anderen ‚versteht‘, d.h. überschaut. Ebenso heißt ‚auf jemanden hören‘ nicht einfach, dass man blindlings tut, was der andere will. Wer so ist, den nennen wir hörig. Offenheit für den anderen schließt also die Anerkennung ein, dass ich in mir etwas gegen mich gelten lassen muß, auch wenn es keinen anderen gäbe, der es gegen mich geltend machte.²⁹

Hier liegt die Entsprechung der hermeneutischen Erfahrung. Ich muß die Überlieferung in ihrem Anspruch gelten lassen, nicht im Sinne einer bloßen Anerkennung der Andersheit der Vergangenheit, sondern in der Weise, daß sie mir etwas zu sagen hat. Auch das verlangt eine grundsätzliche Art der Offenheit. Wer in dieser Weise für die Überlieferung offen ist, durchschaut, daß das historische Bewusstsein gar nicht wirklich offen ist, sondern vielmehr, wenn es seine Texte ‚historisch‘ liest, die Überlieferung immer schon vorgängig und grundsätzlich nivelliert hat, so dass die Maßstäbe des eigenen Wissens durch die Überlieferung niemals in Frage gestellt werden können.³⁰

Hermeneutic openness is required not only with regards to what is being delivered over, but also with regards to the manner in which we ourselves listen to how something is being delivered over to us here and now. The kind of openness matters for interpersonal commitment and the affective and social bond that tie us together and enable us to question our own standards for understanding what it means to belong to a tradition. In the term memory work, this kind of hermeneutic openness is constitutive for how we become capable of attending to collective memory itself. If we mistakenly take collective memory to be *historical* in the way Gadamer describes, namely as repetition or reproduction of the past, we overlook the productive aspect of memory work that in the end allow us to make discoveries about ourselves in the way we respond to the past.

²⁹ Ibid., 367.

³⁰ Ibid., 367.

3. Having to remember, wanting to forget: on clichés and repetition

Bearing Gadamer in mind, we might see the attempt at *mastering* the past being at stake: by turning the past into clichés about everyday events or by wanting to overcome memory work once and for all, the nostalgic historical understanding of the past blocks the possibility of listening to what is being delivered over and thereby the hermeneutic experience of memory work is being prevented. In this section, I will look at Hermann Lübbe's idea of silencing memory work in order to move forward, and in section 4 I will look at Aleida Assmann's idea of possible latency in collective memory. I will argue that both Lübbe and Assmann do not sufficiently account for the interplay between the affective and the reflective aspects of memory work. The two aspects are necessary in order for memory work to be constitutive of a hermeneutic experience that enables us to make discoveries about ourselves as we respond to the past.

As documented by Assmann³¹, there is in the German memory Culture (*Erinnerungskultur*) also a certain discontent (*Unbehagen*) related to the institutionalization of cultural memory of war crimes since 1990's. Hermann Lübbe is someone for whom the discontent has led to a form of saturation with institutionalized memory and acts of atonement. According to Lübbe³² the German people needed to move on after the war, and not only to look backwards with guilt. In 1983 he argued that an intended silence with regards to the German past of WW2 would lead to an integration into the coming of a brighter future. In 2007, Lübbe confirms his integration thesis from 1983: the intended silence has been necessary for the transformation of post-war Germany into a federal democratic republic and for that reason the memories of what happened during the war could not surface right away, silence was the medium needed to change the self-understanding of the German people: "Diese gewisse Stille war das sozialpsychologisch und politisch nötige Medium der Verwandlung unserer Nachkriegsbevölkerung der Bundesrepublik Deutschland."³³

Whereas the silence, according to Lübbe, was the necessary medium politically and socio-psychologically speaking that allowed the German people to restore a kind of normality, the memory culture has since then increasingly intensified. Lübbe argues that instead of the memories wearing off³⁴ they seem to return more intensely the further away in time we move

³¹ Assmann: *Unbehagen*.

³² Hermann Lübbe „*Ich entschuldige mich*“ – *Das neue politische Bußritual*: Berlin 2003; Hermann Lübbe *Vom Parteigenossen zum Bundesbürger: Über beschwiegene und historisierte Vergangenheiten*, München 2007.

³³ Lübbe: *Parteigenossen*, 20.

³⁴ *Ibid.*, 14.

from the Third Reich³⁵. Contrary to Sebald, Lübbe is someone who would disagree that the Germans suffered from collective amnesia with regards to the firebombing and the war in general. Lübbe primarily argued against the Freudian voices of Mitscherlich and Mitscherlich³⁶ who held that Germans were *incapable of mourning* their past and thus had to *repress* it. For something to be repressed in this way, so Lübbe argues, millions of memories would have to be erased; many political actions, literary testimonies, and historiographic writings would have to be ignored; and instead of seeing the politico-moral task of making a postwar German self-understanding suitable and sustainable in for the future (*zukunfts-fähig*), the Mitscherlichs' thesis of collective repression turns this task into a matter of collective or national therapy.³⁷ In Lübbe's view, it seems, there can be no talk of collective amnesia, since everyone remembered what had happened and "Anne Franks Tagesbuch war eine sehr verbreitete Jugend-Lektüre."³⁸ The reasons listed by Lübbe for the impossibility of collective repression and thus of collective amnesia³⁹ are at this level very much align with what Sebald calls out as clichés.⁴⁰ The fact that certain books have become popular among the adolescents by no means suffices to prove that collective memory is not distorted and that the thesis of collective amnesia is false. Sebald's point was exactly that beyond clichés of the ways in which of everyday life continued to go on during and after the war, there was a void of voices and literature dealing with the traumas within families and within society at large.

As the late American philosopher Sue Campbell wrote, commenting on Sebald's lectures and reflecting on the letters that were sent to him as a response to his lectures, the *nostalgic repetition* of the past that singles out only certain details contributes to idealization and is regressive:

Sebald's writing displays that concerns about nostalgic memory are not alleviated by showing that the details remembered are factual – that Karl was in fact in Africa or that baby Bübchen ran naked in the garden. That we can relate certain facts about the past does not prevent recollection from being distorted or inaccurate in a sense of having precisely to do with its selectivity or appropriate significance. Moreover, it is partly the context of collective memory that determines what is distortion and

³⁵ Ibid., 11.

³⁶ Alexander Mitscherlich and Margerete Mitscherlich *Die Unfähigkeit zu trauern: Grundlagen kollektiven Verhaltens*, München 2016.

³⁷ Lübbe: *Parteigenossen*, 23.

³⁸ Ibid., 24. See also the following quote which has a ring of worn out or insincere memorial duty to it: "Keine gymnasiale Gründungsfestschrift versäumt über die 1937er Relegation der jüdischen Schüler zu berichten; keine Kleinstadtchronik erscheint ohne Präsentation eines Fotos der brennenden Synagoge; jede Schülerbücherei führt das Tagebuch der Anne Frank mehrfach; [...] die professionelle Historiographie von Anfang und Ende der Hitler-Diktatur ist regelmäßig bestsellerträchtig.", (*Parteigenossen*, 9)

³⁹ Ibid., 22-25.

⁴⁰ Sebald: *Luftkrieg und Literatur*, 96 ff.

this in two ways. The banal domestic recollections sent to Sebald are nostalgic because they are repeated; moreover, they are repeated in the context of virtual silence about the surrounding destruction – the firestorms, the corpses, the flies, and so on. Their repetition in this context determines a distortion in these memories, a lack of faithfulness to the past that morally reflects on each individual rememberer, but cannot be identified without attention to the social dimensions of recollective activity.⁴¹

Central to Campbell's idea of relational memory is that we cannot separate our own past from the past of others. The idea of responding with clichés of *what else went on* during the war, that children grew bigger, and that some people went on holidays, when it is accompanied with silence concerning the destruction is exactly what points to the distortion of memory:

Questions of memory accuracy, whether the past is faithfully remembered, are thus often much more than questions about whether someone got the details right. They are questions about perspective, about the significance of the past to the present; and we are responsible because we share a past that we witness differently. The failure to give appropriate significance to a shared history of wartime destruction in Germany is manifest in a moral, epistemological, and emotional distortion of individual recollection.⁴²

The role of a cliché in the context of violence, war, and destruction is thus a response within the same register: the violence of a cliché is that of reducing differences in perspectives with regards to memory. It obscures and ignores other people's experiences as rememberers and reduces the context of destruction to the realm of the ordinary. As Campbell's reflection shows, the nostalgic repetition within such a reductive frame prevents each single individual to consider the relational context of collective memory – and importantly this nostalgic reduction contains a violent gesture toward the plurality of perspectives. Nostalgic repetition not only distorts memory; it also annuls the plurality of perspectives for the sake of preserving only one perspective on the past. In this way, nostalgic repetition prevents the hermeneutic openness required for memory work.

4. The role of latency in memory work

The cultural historian Aleida Assmann⁴³ attempts to find a middle ground between the thesis of collective amnesia and the pragmatic integration thesis held by Lübke. Assmann argues that in cases of collective trauma, a certain amount of time must pass for a group to come to terms with the trauma and to begin remembering what in fact has happened. According to Assmann, the memories of German civilians after 1945 were neither repressed nor silenced, the past

⁴¹ Sue Campbell *Our Faithfulness to the Past: The Ethics and Politics of Memory*, Oxford 2014, 25-6.

⁴² *Ibid.*, 26.

⁴³ Assmann: *Unbehagen*; Assmann *Der lange Schatten*.

happenings were kept as latent memories⁴⁴. What Lübbe, according to Assmann, saw with pragmatic eyes was that the transformative power of silence allowed the German people to become capable of finding and seeing the future again. That is, rather than forgetting about the past, a pragmatic amount of silence allowed the German people to keep the memories latent while at the same time not actively taking up the past traumatizing events as questionable:

Durch das Latenthaltend der Vergangenheit wurden gesellschaftliche Konflikte vermieden. Das biographische Innenleben war Privatsache. Es war nach Lübbe eben diese Latenz – hergestellt durch Diskretion und Beschweigen all dessen, was im Erfahrungsgedächtnis millionenfach vorhanden und somit allgemein bekannt war – die der neuen Bundesrepublik zu einer schnellen gesellschaftlichen Integration und zu wirtschaftlichen, Aufschwung verholfen hat. Aus pragmatischer Sicht, da ist Lübbe sicher zuzustimmen, war diese Praxis alternativlos.⁴⁵

According to Assmann, Sebald's lectures are themselves symptomatic as they prove the point of psycho-historical latency⁴⁶. The experiences of the German people during the war an anathema (ibid.,) and Sebald's lectures pointed to the expiration date of the latency phase⁴⁷. With Assmann's idea of latency, a psychological explanation is offered to Sebald's question. So rather than asking why no German authors described what they had been witnessing during the firebombing, we might ask why people do not remember adequately right away and why they do not engage in memory work right away.

Sigmund Freud⁴⁸ argued that traumatic experiences cannot be remembered right away. Traumatic experiences are characterized by the way in which they cannot be turned into memories right away but rather continue to haunt the traumatized persons in the present. The uncontrollable return of the traumatic experience haunts the persons in the present because the events cannot be captured *as* memories but keep being unconsciously re-enacted. On a collective level, we might see how ghosts of the past keep haunting a group when no memory work is being carried out, and when no commitment is made as to consider past events as having happened; rather the group might be stuck in repetition, reenacting the trauma⁴⁹.

⁴⁴ Assmann: *Unbehagen*, 44; *Der lange Schatten*, 185-9.

⁴⁵ Assmann: *Unbehagen*, 45.

⁴⁶ Assmann: *Der lange Schatten*, 185.

⁴⁷ Ibid., 185, 186, 189.

⁴⁸ Sigmund Freud "Trauer und Melancholie" in *Sigmund Freud Studienausgabe*, Bd.III, Frankfurt 2000; Sigmund Freud „Jenseits des Lustprinzips“ in *SigmundFreud Studienausgabe*, Bd. III, Frankfurt 2000; Sigmund Freud „Erinnern, Wiederholen, Durcharbeiten“ in *Sigmund Freud Studienausgabe*, Ergänzungsband, Frankfurt 2000.

⁴⁹ Cathy Caruth *Unclaimed Experiences: Trauma, Narrative, and History*, Baltimore, Maryland 2016.

On the one hand, latency is inherent of traumatic memory. As argued by Freud, memory is distorted in traumatic experiences. The distorted memory can thus be active without being remembered. After working through (in therapy) what has happened the traumatic experience can be remembered properly. Latency serves as a kind of defence mechanism to avoid having to remember what has happened. Acting out what cannot yet be remembered is a result of the nature of traumatic experiences and latency characterizes the phase of acting out where the traumatized subject is stuck in repetition, and at the same time responding to the past⁵⁰. Aleida Assmann applies this Freudian notion of latency with regards to collective memory⁵¹, however she translates it into an *empirical* impossibility of remembering traumas immediately⁵². In traumatic collective memory, according to her, it seems that a period of latency is *required* for something to be remembered. She proposes that some questions will inevitably be left for the next generations because we cannot *yet* remember what has happened due to the traumatic events have imposed on us. Thus, when Sebald critically wonders why in post-war Germany no literary author dealt with the firebombing of German civilians, Assmann answers that a period of latency might have been necessary to deal with the trauma.

The problem with this view is that, contrary to Freud's, we are left with no explanation of this kind of latency other than pragmatic, empirical fact. What for Lübke was part of an integration thesis, is for Assmann simply a fact. However, latency of this kind further requires the absence of reflective voices, and it requires that, as Sebald wrote, a whole generation does not *articulate* what has happened. Maybe part of the years of silence enabled Germany to look forward, but it requires a different answer to understand how it is possible to not *face* the past: Here a more nuanced analysis of the fragility of collective identities and their way of taking up the past would be needed. As argued by Thomas Schwarz Wentzer diachronic commemorating and thereby acts of co-witnessing past events are constitutive of having *been there* as a member of a 'we' that remembers. Wentzer carefully argues that collective memory is not a matter of bringing the past to life by empathy or listing events of the past⁵³. Rather, one's own historicity as a part of group is experienced in acts of remembering a past, also when what we remember are events that we ourselves did not take part in. The act of bearing witness in this sense is an act of becoming a 'we' that remembers; a 'we' that is engaged in memory work, we could say.

⁵⁰ Line Ryberg Ingerslev "Tendency, Repetition, and the Activity of the Mind in Traumatic Experiences" in *Human Studies*, vol.: 47:1, 207-228.

⁵¹ Assmann: *Der lange Schatten*, 183 ff.

⁵² Assmann: *Unbehagen*, 56-9.

⁵³ Thomas Schwarz Wentzer "Vermächtnis und Geschichte: Überlegungen zu Figuren responsiver Geschichtlichkeit im Anschluss an Waldenfels" in *Deutsche Zeitschrift für Philosophie*, 68(1): 121-138.

Transgenerational witnessing⁵⁴, as Wentzer argues, amounts to a form of cross temporal co-witnessing and *being there* as a member of a diachronic ‘we’. Latency according to Wentzer’s view could be understood as a productive diachronicity in the Gadamerian sense such that historicity is not first and foremost experienced directly but is existentially lived and constituted by acts of group memory where the ‘we’ remembers and witnesses its own past. In this sense, latency is irreducible to a psycho-historical fact but is tied to a question of self-understanding which ethically motivates memory work. Just as the uncontrollable return of traumatic experiences cannot be turned into proper memories of the past simply by conscious control or will, just as impossible is it to turn memory work into a maxim for collective self-understanding. This is why the motivation has to be ethical. The Israeli author Yishai Sarid provides a terrifying and brilliant example of the possible dangers of such an attempt in his book “The Memory Monster⁵⁵”. In the absence of ethically guided memory work, affectivity can turn collective memory into a blind educational industry.

5. The ethical motivation of memory work

As has been shown, the role of latency in collective memory is poorly understood when we look at it primarily as an empirical fact, because when we do so, we overlook the existential and ethical motivation to respond to the past as a way of coming to understand oneself as member of a certain group and the other way around as well, as a way of coming to understand the kind of ‘we’ to which many different perspectives belong and participate over time. I have proposed that one form of group remembering is memory work and I will further argue that we ought to engage in this form of group remembering as it allows us to revise our collective self-understanding. In the following, I will argue that memory work for groups ought to be ethically motivated. Questions pertaining to memory work that are carried by an ethical motivation would be questions that resemble the following: Are there perspectives we have failed to attend to with regards to how we remember the past? Are there questions with regards to how we remember the past that we have not yet asked or haven’t asked thoroughly enough? How does our understanding of the past contextualize in the present day with the knowledge we have of past oppression and suffering of others?

⁵⁴ Thomas Schwarz Wentzer “‘Ich habe Königsberg brennen sehen‘ – Überlegungen zu Responsivität geschichtlicher Erfahrung und den Erfahrungscharakter der Responsivität“ in *Danish Yearbook of Philosophy*, vol. 48-9, 153-168.

⁵⁵ Yishai Sarid *The Memory monster*, translated by Yardenne Greenspan. New York 2020.

The Canadian philosopher Lisa Guenther has argued that beyond the social dimension of collective memory there is as well an ethical dimension to memory⁵⁶. Whereas the social dimension consists in the negotiation among different groups of how to understand the past with regards to social identities, the ethical dimension is independent of any such social belonging and identification. Rather, she argues, the ethical dimension of memory is experienced as a demand to remember:

We could understand this dimension of collective memory as an ethical response to (the memories) of others: a way of remembering forward that relies not on the present recollection of one's own past experience but rather on one's *relation to the time of the Other*, to a past that was never present (at least, not for me). Whether or not I have a direct connection to this past – for example, as a descendant of victims or perpetrators – I am ethically commanded to remember that history *so that it may never again be repeated*.⁵⁷

In listening to what is being delivered over, rather than studying the past historically, for instance, or primarily as a matter of social identity, there is a Levinasian demand to *remember and thus to listen to the sufferance of the other*. Surely, there are other obligations to remember than simply those of acknowledging the sufferance of others, we might argue, but in experiencing the demand, I am, according to Guenther, addressed in the second person to acknowledge past violence and oppression. We might say with Gadamer, as developed in section 2, that we are demanded to keep the hermeneutic openness possible when we listen to what is being delivered over. Importantly, in arguing that the demand is independent of one's social identity, Guenther argues differently than for instance Margalit, who holds that one should only remember the past of those that one has formed thick relations with.⁵⁸

The ethical dimension of collective memory is not simply an imaginary act of thinking about oppression or violence, it consists in the ethical response to being addressed. I respond to this address by committing myself to the memory work. To put it differently, we can say that by going beyond the social dimension of collective memory, a person is ethically motivated to engage in memory work. This is Guenther's point, as she argues that the ethical response is *not* a point of identification. To engage in memory work is to surpass the level of identification in the way that my response no longer constitutes my belonging to this or that group. As argued, memory work can guide a group to revise its self-understanding; the motivation of this

⁵⁶ Lisa Guenther "Collective Memory at Canada's Prison for Women" in *Critical Times*, 7:2, 260-79.

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*, 270.

⁵⁸ Avishai Margalit *The Ethics of Memory*.

orientation ought to be ethical and thus, here I would agree with Guenther, it takes us beyond the question of identification.

The practical implications of the ethical dimension of memory prevent a narrow and one-sided version of past events from serving as justification for further acts of oppression. The ethical dimension of memory will address us continuously to respond to the past. Memory work might entail possible discoveries and might lead to plural self-transformation. Because of this responsive dynamic, memory work builds on *listening and responding* to the past, rather than repeating it for the sake of thickening our relations.⁵⁹

In order to get clearer on how memory work might be ethically motivated it will be helpful to distinguish between pre-reflective plural self-understanding and reflective plural self-understanding. To illustrate the difference, I draw on Patrizio Lo Presti's Brandomian argument concerning the use of the 1st person plural pronoun "We"⁶⁰. The question is which kind of practical know-how someone must have in order to say 'we' and further, which kind of reasoning someone must be capable of exercising when using the concept 'we'⁶¹? According to Lo Presti, in pre-reflective plural self-awareness "the 'We' is transparent' to participants. One acts, thinks and in general is, and has the world in view from a pre-reflective first-personal plural self-perspective. *It* – the plural self-perspective – isn't reflected on⁶²" On this stage, participants to a 'we' are "doing something implicitly: making, transforming, and possibly giving expression to the propriety-assessings of participants to a pre-reflective plural self⁶³" If we were to link this kind of pre-reflective plural self-awareness to memory, an implicit pre-reflective plural memory would be an unreflective embodied, practical awareness of 'how we do this or that' and an implicit participation in plural narratives of 'who we are'. Having grown up in Denmark, to give an example, I am (affectively and pre-reflectively) familiar with characters from children's television programs from the 80'ies, implicitly this is at the backbones of my affective collective memory⁶⁴. In this case, I am part of a 'we' that tacitly has certain views on what a good program for children should look like; assertive and anarchistic puppets must challenge the authorities, say.

⁵⁹ See discussion in Line Ryberg Ingerslev "Responding to the Past: Affectivity and Reflectivity in Collective Memory" (Forthcoming)

⁶⁰ Patrizio Lo Presti "Between Doing and Saying 'We' – On analytic Pragmatism and the Progressive Development of Plural Self-Expression" in *Contemporary Pragmatism* 21,120-153.

⁶¹ *Ibid.*,124.

⁶² *Ibid.*,141.

⁶³ *Ibid.*,142.

⁶⁴ Erll: *Hidden Power*, Wertsch: *Collective Memory*, Gadamer: *Wahrheit und Methode*.

Now, in order for a group to be able to self-reflect, some sensitivity to normative regulations must be available. However, for a group to be capable of ‘plural self-explication’ group-members will be able to make use of the conditionals involved in their collective reasoning: according to Lo Presti, the group thereby assess itself in terms of *reasoning*:

Plural self-explication is explication of inferential relations among properties embedded in plural self-constitutive normative regularities. Thus, paradigmatically, plural self-explication involves the use of conditionals; e.g. ‘If we’re committed to this, we have to change’ or ‘If we do it, we’ll never be forgiven.’ This is to expressively lay bare the normative fine structure of ‘who “We” are’. Making those proprieties explicit is making them available for reasoning, for demands of justification.⁶⁵

While keeping the children shows in mind, we can imagine a slightly different kind of narrative that we then later in life come to assess and that, were we to look at gender role or racial stereotyping according to how we present them to our children today ‘we would never be forgiven’.

According to Lo Presti, it is on the stage of explicit reflective plural-awareness that a group can *commit* or *stop to commit* to what was hitherto inherent to the group’s self-understanding:

Now becoming explicitly plurally self-aware of that ingrained commitment, participants face a stark choice: either to plurally self-terminate – to wholesale abandon plural self-constitutive normative regularities – or to radically plurally self-transform – to uproot the discordant strings of commitment and consequently update all those affected by it (downstream, of conclusions from it) and those from which commitment or entitlement to it can be inferred (upstream, as premises for it).⁶⁶

The implications of this Brandomian thought of what we are practically committed to and entitled to in when we say ‘We’ shows that the normative status involved in saying ‘we’ is one that commits us to doing things in a certain way; we hold each other responsible for articulating the normative significance of what is implied in saying ‘we’ in this particular way⁶⁷. With regards to collective memory and memory work, the distinction between implicit plural self-awareness and plural self-reflection helps us be more specific with regards to the possible ethical motivation behind memory work. The practical rationality of groups remembering and responding to their past in which they might as individuals have been directly involved can be understood in a similar way. In saying that ‘we remember such-and-such event’ entails a practical commitment to giving and asking for further reasons within the field of collective

⁶⁵ Lo Presti: *Between Doing and Saying ‘We’*, 145.

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*, 144-5. Lo Presti interestingly mentions a third logical option, namely that despite the plural reasoning involved, the participants do nothing; that is, they become subjects to hypocrisy and plural self-deception.

⁶⁷ Robert B. Brandom *Articulation Reasons: An Introduction to Inferentialism*. Harvard 2000, 190-4.

memory, i.e., the practical field of saying ‘we’ with respect to collective memory is making oneself available for memory work on an individual and collective level. What matters for my present inquiry, therefore, is this latter level of commitment and recommitment where a group is involved in a self-explicatory act *of discovery*. As argued by Lo Presti, facing the stark choice of committing to an update of the plural reason-giving system or to engage in an act of self-termination with regards to past actions and values⁶⁸. When we come to discover the past anew or as different from how we took it to have been, we engage in an act of plural self-explication.

The idea of plural self-discovery entails an act of practical deliberation where a group will be making explicit the limitations of a collectively held past self-understanding. This thought can be understood if we recall Bernard Williams’ idea of practical oughts and bear our focus of plural self-reflection in mind. Whereas a *moral* ‘ought’ is grounded in norms, Williams argues that a *practical* ‘ought’ reflects the a person’s or a group’s *character*⁶⁹. Williams argues that because of our incapacities, what we cannot do and what is thus practically impossible for someone to do reveals this person’s character. When someone concludes that something can’t be done, what is recognized is an *incapacity*. The character of a person or a group is revealed by this person’s or group’s practical incapacities.⁷⁰

We are subject to the model that what one can do sets the limits to deliberation, and that character is revealed by what one chooses within those limits, among the things that one can do. But character (of a person in the first instance; but related points apply to a group, or to a tradition) is equally revealed in the location of those limits, and in the very fact that one can determine, sometimes through deliberation itself, that one cannot do certain things, and must do others. Incapacities can not only set limits to character and provide condition of it, but can also partly constitute its substance.⁷¹

How does the idea of incapacity of character relate to plural self-reflection with regards to memory work? Williams argues that a practical ought is “heavily governed by actual reality” and thus to what agents are actually capable and incapable of doing, intentionally⁷² A practical ought therefore “implies possibility, will be exclusive, and will be relative to the projects of the agent in question”⁷³. The point is here, that if we *reduce* practical deliberation to moral deliberation, then we exclude my projects and the nature of my character from being relevant to practical deliberation. This particular emphasis on possibility, exclusivity, and relativity to

⁶⁸ Ibid., see chapter 5.

⁶⁹ Bernard Williams *Moral Luck*, Cambridge 1981, 131.

⁷⁰ Ibid., 129.

⁷¹ Ibid., 130.

⁷² Ibid., 117-8.

⁷³ Ibid., 120.

an agent's project is important in relation to collective memory. *As it turns out, the limits set to how a group is prepared to deal with the past reveal the character of this group or tradition and these limits are dynamic and transformative.* The practical obligation tied to memory work entails the possibility of discovery related one's self-understanding: "to arrive at the conclusion that one must do a certain thing is typically, to make a discovery – a discovery which is, always minimally and sometimes substantially, a discovery about oneself."⁷⁴ In relation to memory work this discovery might entail that we think differently about the past and about ourselves because we understand the past in a new light. The kind of discovery that can be made is the one Lo Presti describes as 'facing a stark choice' to as a group either self-terminate or to commit to transformation – say if one's collective self-understanding by way of a reconfiguration of the memory landscape. It is at this level of plural self-reflection that a group engages in *memory work* and makes explicit to itself how it stands with regards to the past and with regards to how to deal with the past in the present.

6. We Apologize – Assuming responsibility anew for the past

In what remains of this paper, I will turn to the role of public apologies as a way of illustrating how Lo Presti's notion of plural self-reflection can be put to work. To disclaim the past collectively relies on a practice enabled by plural self-reflection. The official apology is one candidate for this kind of practice that allows for and is enabled by an ethically motivated collective self-reflection that might lead us to *change* our ways of acting. As a result of what has been developed in this paper, we can see how two conditions will have to obtain for someone who makes a genuine public apology *on behalf* of a group. One needs a) to *be a committed part* of that group; and to b) *not condone* the reasoning that led the group to perform the action. What this shows us is that in order to perform a genuine public apology, one must have engaged in memory work in the sense discussed above. Hence, we can see that the notion of memory work has explanatory power beyond the field of local debates of collective memory; it can help us assess the kind of responsibility involved in transtemporal collective actions and it can show how a mode of plural self-reflection is enabled by memory work. To show this is the aim of this section.

We would need to distinguish public apologies from forms of individual self-defence and personal apologies; a public apology is not just an enlarged version of interpersonal

⁷⁴ Ibid., 130.

apologies^{75, 76, 77}. Public apologies constitute a form of moral argument, the purpose of which is to relate particular policies to shared norms and to respond appropriately where transgressions have occurred⁷⁸. At this point we can say that a public apology is an act of *making explicit* – in the Brandomian sense and as developed above with Lo Presti – and thereby of responding to the wrongdoings and the harm that a group of people have suffered due to acts of reasoning that has not been made explicit as causing harm. This speech act, in and of itself contains the possibility for a powerful transformation, as Lo Presti argued: as a group becomes plurally self-aware of the ingrained commitment of one’s reasoning, its members are faced with a stark choice to either self-terminate or to radically plurally self-transform⁷⁹. To actively respond to the kind of stark choice can lead to a public apology. Not only does a public apology attempt to institute and enable further plural self-reflection. It furthermore *inscribes into language* the existence of oppressive behaviour and structural injustice by presenting itself as a disclaiming of the past. An official apology is thus more than just a speech act, because it enables a mode of reflection for a group to disclaim its past and to reflect on the existing norms and the aspirations for future generations. It induces a mode of critique and enables forms of commitment to values and aspirations that have not consciously been appraised, or might have been forgotten, or that might not have been publicly recognized. To disclaim the past collectively relies on a practice that allows for plural self-reflection. The official apology is one candidate for a kind of practice that allows for collective moral reflection that might lead us to change our ways of acting.

If we take the act of publicly apologizing as an example of a Saying that by far surpasses what is said in the Levinasian sense, we can at the same time unfold what we mean by inscribing past events into language. As a case of dynamic repetition, the past is remembered anew and again but while making explicit by an act of plural self-reflection that a group takes on the responsibility for past events. The public apology inscribes unrecognized past events into language and as such into the collective mind and by doing so, the saying itself surpasses what is said. What is said contains facts about the past that might have been known to all, and the

⁷⁵ Lisa Storm Villadsen “Beyond the Spectable of Apologia: Official Apologies as Proto-Deliberative Rhetoric Instantiations of Rhetorical Citizenship” in *Quarterly Journal of Speech*, 2012 Vol. : 98:2, 230-247.

⁷⁶ Lisa Storm Villadsen “Introduction: Citizenship as a Rhetorical Practice” in *Rhetorical Citizenship and Public Deliberation* (Eds.) C.E. Koch & L. Villadsen, Pennsylvania State 2012, 4-15.

⁷⁷ Lisa Storm Villadsen “More than a nice ritual: Official Apologies as a rhetorical act in need of theoretical reconceptualization.” In *Let’s talk politics. New essays on deliberative rhetorics*. (Eds.) H.v. Belle, K. Rutten, P. Gillaerts, et.al. 2014: John Hopkins Publishing Company, 27-43.

⁷⁸ Villadsen *More than a nice ritual*, 28.

⁷⁹ Lo Presti *Between Doing and Saying ‘We’*, 145.

Saying in and of itself acknowledges the unsaid and thereby enables a plural self-transformation. At this point, we are back at where we started: the possible ethical motivation of acts of plural self-reflection. To articulate and inscribe what was hitherto unsaid into language differs from describing and listing historical events. Making explicit the implications of a collective's past reasoning entails a break in the collective's self-understanding; we can no longer continue in this way. We must change our practices and acknowledge that harm was done. Memory work contributes to the process of making explicit the unknown implication of past reasoning while methodologically foregrounding the temporal distance and seeking hermeneutical openness. Both Peter Goldie⁸⁰ and Jonathan Lear⁸¹ would point out that there a certain irony might be involved in memory work. A certain gap arises between how things seemed to us then and how they look to us now. The gap is experienced as a tension between an earlier response and an external perspective of the same event where the gap reveals "that one is failing to have the appropriate emotional response from the external perspective that the 'art of recollection' requires⁸²." Here the art of recollection would acquire the same kind of 'effort and responsibility'⁸³ that is required for memory work. In Lear's case, an ironic experience is one of not knowing how to live up to one's practical identity and that making oneself available to the kind of questioning that is also part of memory work is at the same time a serious commitment to being who one is⁸⁴. We can see how the irony of not yet knowing the possible harms of our current ignorance will be part of the seriousness with which we insist on the possibility of coming to a halt as a group, while we question our past reasoning. The public apology marks the point in time in which we stand in such a gap; we make explicit by telling and showing that we see both perspectives at the same time and acknowledge the harm that we have caused in the past as we inscribe it into language for future generations to contain in their reflections.

In this short reflection on the public apology as an example of the ethical motivation of memory work, I do not consider the apparent problems with regards to official apologies: namely that they are susceptible to ideological criticism and called for scepticism. They are often politically motivated, they often come across as insincere, they can be accused of being untimely or temporally suspect, and sometimes the public apology only points to the hypocrisy of political

⁸⁰ Peter Goldie "Grief: A Narrative Account" in *Ratio*, XXIV (2):119-137; Peter Goldie *The Mess Inside: Narrative, Emotion, and the Mind*, Oxford 2012.

⁸¹ Jonathan Lear *A Case for Irony*. Cambridge 2011.

⁸² Goldie *The Mess Inside*, 70 ff.

⁸³ *Ibid.*

⁸⁴ Lear: *Irony*, 21,30.

regimes, people in power, structural injustice etc., as when the act of apologizing does not lead to any plural self-reflection at all. But what the short reflection is meant to achieve is to make clear how we do commit to memory work on a collective level and how this kind of work is ethically motivated and expressive of a change in our reasoning about ourselves as part of a temporally enduring we.

7. Conclusion: Reconfiguration of Memory Landscapes

What does it mean for a group to remember? How can we ethically respond to the past? I have argued that the memory work is an active stance of self-reflection held by a collective in taking up its past with the aim of making explicit some of the underlying mechanisms that have prevented this group for understanding aspects of its own past. Memory work thereby involves self-transformation through an interplay between processes of identification or affective belonging on the one hand and dis-identification or reflective alienation, on the other: To understand oneself anew through the past involves affectivity that repeats for the sake of questioning and discovering who we have become, and by dynamic repetition the past is transformed as a matter of becoming⁸⁵ (Ingerslev forthcoming, 2024b, 2022). By facing the past as a question of collective self-understanding, we participate to reconfigurations of the memory landscape. We set up an ethical mark for future orientation when we engage in memory work and further when as a result of memory work a public apology inscribes into language a before and an after of recognizing past sufferings. Affectivity and latency might play a role in how we come to take up the implicit collective memory, but latency in and of itself does not prevent us from dealing with the traumatic past or traumatizing present. I have argued that memory work *ought* to be ethically motivated and that we can think of memory work with the aim of inscribing into language the harms and wrong-doings of a group. Literature, the arts, and philosophical reflections play the same role with regards to this kind of inscription; an ethically motivated writing that inscribes into language the act of taking responsibility for thought and for human, plural self-understanding. For this reason, latency alone is neither an excuse nor an explanation for not facing the past.⁸⁶

⁸⁵ Line Ryberg Ingerslev “Grief” in *Routledge Handbook of Phenomenology of Emotions*, (Eds.) Thomas Szanto & Hilge Landweer, London 2022; Ingerslev “Responding to the Past”, Line Ryberg Ingerslev “What the Experience of Transience Can Tell Us About the Afterlife” 2024 in *TheoLogica* 8:1, 60-77.

⁸⁶ The present work has been supported by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Horizons 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement nr. 832940). Earlier versions of this paper were presented at the “Residenzvorlesung” held at Universität Würzburg (June 2024) and at the “Singularity and the We” conference held at University of Copenhagen (September 2024). I am grateful to the audience present at those occasions for helpful questions and comments.